

***Polyommatus amandus* (Schneider, 1792): historical, geographical, and bionomic overview of Hungary and Carpathian–Pannonian Basin (Lepidoptera, Lycaenidae)**

Imre Fazekas

Abstract. *Polyommatus amandus* (Schneider, 1792) is a rare Lycaenid species in Hungary and Carpathian–Pannonian Basin, living in local populations. Starting from the 19th century, the author collected and reviewed observations and information on the geographical distribution and bionomics of the species. This is the first study in Hungary to present the literature of a protected species in chronological order. The study includes several photos that are important for identification, along with an illustration of male genitalia. He critically analyzes previously depicted distribution maps of the Carpathian–Pannonian region and presents a new geographical distribution pattern. He also summarized and annotated the Central European literature on the species.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Lycaenidae, *Polyommatus amandus*, distribution, bionomy

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Introduction

Information about the species *Polyommatus amandus* is scattered throughout Hungarian literature, with several publications containing contradictory information. I (Fazekas 1987) first collected the species near the Austrian border (Sopron). My publication on this subject appeared in a local journal that was difficult to access and only available in print, thus escaping the attention of researchers. The new site I discovered in 1987 significantly changed the pattern of the species' geographical distribution in Hungary. The habitat types also differed from those known until then.

Polyommatus amandus is a protected species in Hungary and is listed in the Red Book. Its IUCN classification is LC. In the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List, the category LC (Least Concern) denotes species that are not currently facing a significant risk of extinction. Species classified as LC typically exhibit large or stable populations and do not meet the quantitative thresholds associated with threatened categories such as Near Threatened, Vulnerable, Endangered, or Critically Endangered. Consequently, an LC designation indicates that, based on available data, the species is of relatively low conservation risk. However, there are no stable populations of this species in Hungary; it has disappeared from many of its former habitats and has not been observed there for decades. In my opinion, it is in sharp decline. This is confirmed by publications and observations since the end of the 19th century. According to these observations, a recent revision of threatened butterfly species in Hungary indicated NT (Near Threatened) status (Gergely & Hudák 2021). While generally a local species in Europe, in some other areas, e.g. in the Balkans, (Stara Planina – a non-calcareous habitat) it is relatively common (Gergely P. pers comm.).

In this study, I synthesize for the first time in Hungary, in chronological order, the most important knowledge we have had about the species since the mid-19th century. I also provide a brief overview of the Central European region.

Materials and methods

The study is based on the systematic examination of 6 entomological collections containing Hungarian specimens of *P. amandus*. To facilitate precise taxonomic identification and evaluate morphological variation, six male specimens were subjected to genital dissection and comparative structural analysis. The flight period and seasonal activity patterns were established primarily through the analysis of temporal data from the examined collections. Bibliographic data from relevant literature were utilized exclusively as supplementary evidence to support the primary collection-based findings. Data concerning larval host plants and habitat preferences were compiled from three primary sources: Original field observations and primary data were recorded by the author, verified personal communications from professional colleagues, synthesized records from established entomological references and monographs. All primary data, including the comprehensive electronic database (MS Excel), are curated and archived at the Pannon Institute (Pécs, Hungary).

Results

Polyommatus amandus (Schneider, 1792)

Papilio amandus Schneider, 1792, Neuestes Magazin für die Liebhaber der Entomologia 1:428

Syn.: *Papilio icarius* Esper, 1793

Diagnosis. Wingspan 27–35 mm Male: The dorsal wing surface is a deep, highly iridescent sky blue with a violet hue. The marginal borders are narrow, dark, and diffused, lacking a distinct outline or further markings. Female: The dorsal surface is predominantly brown, characterized by a submarginal band of orange-red spots and a series of marginal dots, which are particularly prominent on the hindwings. Both sexes: The fringes are consistently white. Underside: The ground color of the underside is light slate gray in males and yellowish gray in females. The post-discal eyespots are well-developed, although individual spots may occasionally be absent. In males, the markings on the forewing are often faint or reduced.

Egg: whitish, honeycomb-like surface structure with serrated projections. Larvae: green with yellowish side stripes.

Fig. 1. Diagnostic characters (indicated) of *Polyommatus amandus*

Similar species

***P. bellargus*:** Males are shiny azure, blue. Females are brown with blue scales. Fringes are strongly chequered.

***P. daphnis*:** Hindwings are scalloped – more striking in females. No orange marginal lunules on undersides.

***P. dorylas*:** Males are shiny blue with slight turquoise sheen. Females are brown – with occasional blue scales. Margins of undersides of both wings are pale grey.

***P. icarus*:** No dark marginal border and no darker veins on males. Orange marginal lunules on females on both wings. Intradiscal spot(s) on forewing underside.

***P. thersites*:** Both sexes are like *P. icarus*, but usually smaller. Andriconal scales form a lighter basal area in males. No intradiscal spot on forewing underside.

Male genitalia. For identification purposes, it is best to examine the apex of the valva, which is morphologically similar to the *thersites* species, but the differences are clearly recognizable (see figures 2ab). Higgins (1975, pp. 158–159) provided a good overview of this in his book.

Fig. 2. Diagnostic characters (indicated) of *Polyommatus amandus* male genitalia: **2a)** Sopron-Görbehalom, gen.prep. No. 1740. I. Fazekas **2b)** Comparative drawing of *P. amandus* and *P. thersites* valva (dorso-distal faces)

Geographical distribution. North Africa, Europe (except Great Britain, northern Scandinavia, central and northern France, Belgium and the Netherlands), Turkey, Russia to the Far East.

In various publications, maps showing the geographical distribution of the species in Europe, but mainly in Central Europe, are rough and their patterns are inaccurate (e.g. Higgins & Riley 1971, p. 264). In fact, there is no continuous distribution pattern, only population fragments.

Fig. 3. Distribution pattern of *Polyommatus amandus* in Hungary and its surroundings.

Fig. 4. The fragmented geographical distribution pattern of *Polyommatus amandus* in the Western Palearctic. The proportion of areas from which there are no reliable observations is significant. The arrows indicate hypothetical directions of spread. There are surprisingly isolated populations in the Carpathian-Pannonian region.

Overview of the species in Hungary

1846

In his early work, Nendtvich (1846) mentions the species from Pécs (Mecsek Mountains) under the name "*icarius*." *There have been no reliable observations from the mountain range or its wider surroundings in the past 180 years.*

1868

In his book entitled "The Little Butterfly Collector," Gusztáv Emich writes that it is not uncommon in the Buda-Pest area (known as *Lycaena amanda* or *icarius*).

1896

Abafi-Aigner et al. (1896) mentioned six sites in the territory of what is known as historical Hungary. After the Treaty of Trianon (2021), only the sites in Budapest and Pécs remained. The location of Pécs has certainly only survived in literary terms.

1907

Abafi-Aigner (1907) writes in the first significant Hungarian book on butterflies that it can be found sporadically in two generations from May to August in the country. The larvae live on *Vicia cracca* from April to July.

1953

After World War II, Kovács (1953) compiled the first comprehensive Hungarian monograph on Lepidoptera in the 20th century. In this publication, he describes seven locations where *P. amandus* can be found: the Gödöllő hills, Mecsek mountains, Vértes mountains, and Buda hills. We do not know exactly what he based his claim of its occurrence in the Mecsek Mountains on, but I assume that he repeated old literary data without authentic specimens from collections to prove his point.

1956

Szabó (1956) wrote a monograph on the Hungarian Lycaenidae fauna. He reports that this species was found in only a few locations in the country and was one of the rarest species. He named only the towns of Szár and Pomáz as important locations. He attributes the rarity to Hungary's specific climatic factors, noting that the host plant (*Vicia cracca*) is widespread. He does not provide any explanation of what he means by "specific climatological factors". Szabó did not mention the occurrence of the species in the Mecsek Mountains.

1968

Gozmány (1968) published the species under the name "*Lysandra icarius* ESP." According to him, it is known to occur in only a few locations in Hungary and is very rare, for example, in the Mecsek Mountains (? see above), the Transdanubian Mountains, and the Gödöllő Hills. There is no information on its occurrence in western Hungary and the flatlands. It flies from late May to early June each year. Its host plant is *Vicia cracca*. The author did not include illustrations of the species in his book.

1979

Rézbányai (1979) reported it from the ancient pine–oak forest in Fenyőfő (Northern Bakony Mountains). He considered it a Siberian faunal element, suggesting that it may have arrived there during occasional wandering. He regarded the so-called "primeval forest" as a postglacial relic, with forest clearings dominated by sand steppe. The extent to which the association is truly "ancient"-that is, to what degree it represents a remnant of the original forest-is questionable, since according to contemporary sources, excessive logging presumably led to the near-complete disappearance of pine forests from the northern Bakony foothills during the Middle Ages. According to Habitats of Hungary: Description and Identification of Vegetation

Figs 5. The pattern on the upper (left) and lower (right) sides of the wings of *Polyommatus amandus* ♂: Hungary, Sopron-Görbehalom, 18.vi.1978, leg. Fazekas I. (photo: © Henn T.)

Types (Bölöni et al. 2011), the habitat of *P. amandus* is "Calcareous pine forest" [N2]. In Fenyőfő, bauxite mining and forestry have practically eliminated the former stands. In my opinion, the species has probably become extinct in this area.

1987

According to Fazekas (1987) *Plebicula amanda* Schneider (former name of *P. amandus*) is one of the rarest lycaenid butterflies in Central Europe, with historical records indicating a formerly wider but now severely fragmented distribution in Hungary. Many earlier populations documented from the Mecsek, Bakony, Buda Hills, and Gödöllő Hills appear to have disappeared during the 20th century. This study reports a new occurrence of the species from Sopron-Görbehalom in the eastern Alpine foothills, collected in 1978, providing crucial evidence that this species persists in western Hungary. The habitat consists of streamside meadows and transitional wet grasslands, where *P. amanda* flies alongside several ecologically sensitive Lepidoptera, underscoring the importance of conserving these semi-natural habitats. The two male specimens collected are kept at the Komló Natural History Collection (see in Fig. 4.)

In addition to faunistic data, this study addresses the long-standing taxonomic ambiguity surrounding the placement of *P. amanda*. Through a comparative assessment of morphological traits, host-plant associations, and zoogeographical patterns, this study supports the use of the genus *Plebicula* Higgins, 1969, for the Hungarian fauna, distinguishing it from *Lysandra* and *Agrodiaetus*. These results highlight the biogeographical significance of both species and the need for an updated systematic treatment within Lycaenidae. These findings contribute to ongoing conservation and taxonomic efforts aimed at clarifying the status of rare Eurasian butterfly taxa.

1989

Varga (1989) describes it as a potentially endangered species in the Hungarian Red Book. It lives in forest clearings and fresher steppes, but mostly in small numbers and isolated populations. There are years when the species almost completely disappears, then reappears. The author does not mention any data on distribution.

1994

According to Bálint (1994), "*Polyommatus amandus* is found everywhere in limestone areas in Hungary. This statement cannot be proven. The populations are scattered and their numbers are low. No one has yet researched its biology in Hungary, so we do not have reliable information about the caterpillars' food plants, for example." Bálint (1996, 2006) contradicts his earlier statement when he specifically names the larvae's food plants.

1996

Bálint (1996) began publishing a series of books entitled "Butterflies of the Carpathian Basin." The series, which promises to be excellent, remains unfinished to date. He wrote the following about the species' habitat types and biology: it lives in mountain hay meadows, lush, abandoned hillside and mountain orchards, fresh meadows, and pastures. The main source of nectar for adults is *Centaurea* and *Vicia* flowers. In Pomáz, they most often sucked on meadow sage (*Salvia pratensis*), not on legumes (Gergely P. pers. comm.). Males fly quickly, while females sit in the grass, flying from late May to mid-July. It is a protected butterfly species. The theoretical value is 10,000 HUF.

1997

According to Dietzel (1997), this species is among the rarer Lycaenidae found in Hungary. Although its host plants, species of *Vicia*, are relatively common, the sporadic distribution of the butterfly remains unexplained. In the Bakony Mountains, the species typically occupies mesophilic habitats. It is known to occur in large numbers only in the Balaton Uplands. Dietzel (1997) also emphasized that recent land parceling and other detrimental human activities have increasingly threatened the survival of existing populations. Wooded meadows have been rapidly disappearing due to the establishment of riding trails and seasonal grazing. In addition, larger backyards and orchards are sometimes treated with self-propelled spraying machines; in such cases, poor air circulation exacerbates the spread and impact of chemical drift. In June 1996, Dietzel observed an extremely small population on the southwestern margin of Kab Hill and concluded that the long-term survival of this population fragment in its degraded habitat was highly uncertain.

2006

Bálint et al. (2006) published a catalogue in book form based on the collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum. They provide the label data for all museum specimens, the collection intensity, and the drawing time for the period between 1875 and 2005. The habitat types they report are grassy slopes and forest steppes in low and medium mountain ranges. A new finding regarding the larvae's food plants is that they also name *Lathyrus pratensis*, *Coronilla coronatus*, and *Medicago falcata*.

Fazekas (2006), referring to the earlier publication by Balogh (1978; = *icarius*), reported a specimen collected in June 1891 from Pécs (Mecsek Mountains) (leg. Viertl). The specimen, however, is no longer available for verification. During the past 100 years, *P. amandus* has not been recorded in the Mecsek Mountains, and the species should therefore be considered extinct in this region. Perhaps it would be more accurate to describe it as an extinct or regressing species. It is noteworthy that several extensive areas within the mountains provide suitable habitat conditions for the species, some of which are designated as Natura 2000 sites. Nevertheless, no recent observations have been made. Figure 5 shows the habitats in the Eastern Mecsek Mountains where *P. amandus* could potentially occur. The necessary food plants and nectar sources are also present. Despite this, and despite 50 years of intensive research, the species has not been observed.

2010

Situated on the border of the village of Barabás, along the Ukrainian Hungarian frontier, the southern portion of Kaszonyi Hill represents the remnants of a contemporary island volcano extending into Hungary. This 159.8-hectare area serves as a significant biodiversity hotspot. Rising abruptly from the Beregi Plain, Kaszonyi Hill features a characteristic plateau-like summit; at an elevation of 240 meters above sea level, it constitutes the highest point in Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County. Geologically, the volcano was active during the Middle Pleistocene epoch. The flora of this volcanic formation is notably diverse, exhibiting a unique dual character: the eastern slopes are dominated by species typical of the Carpathian Mountains, whereas the south-southwestern aspects are characterized by grassland and plant communities indigenous to the Great Hungarian Plain. The arboreal vegetation primarily compris-

Fig. 6. Potential habitats of *Polyommatus amandus* in the Eastern Mecsek Mountains in 2024-2025: The area around the town of Váralja. See the text for details.

es silver linden ravine forests and sessile oak forests; however, the mountain's rocky grassland communities also represent high conservation value. In this mosaic of habitats, Varga (2010) identified a population of *Polyommatus amandus*. These observations were recorded within the so-called Tatar maple-sessile oak forest, which is regarded as a relict forest type. According to Varga's findings, this habitat shares structural similarities with the loess oak forests of the Bükk foothills. Notably, despite intensive research in the Mátra, Bükk, and Zemplén Mountains, as well as the Aggtelek Karst region, the species has not been documented in those areas. In my opinion, Varga's discovery is of historical biogeographical significance, as it confirms the occurrence of *Polyommatus amandus* in the lowlands of the Carpathian-Pannonian Basin. This is most likely a relict fragment of a former metapopulation connection with the Carpathian Mountains.

2007

Szeőke (2007) reported it from Gánt in the Vértes Mountains under the name "*Lysandra icarius*." The species was not considered significant in fauna analysis, even though its observation is of outstanding importance from a nature conservation and fauna history perspective.

2017

The most comprehensive and informative book on Hungarian diurnal species is that of Gergely et al. (2017), which contains extensive descriptions and distribution maps. According to the authors, *P. amandus* is a rare mesophilic-hygrophilous species in Hungary, mainly found in the Transdanubian Mountains. It is no longer mentioned in the south of the Mecsek Mountains, but new data have been reported from the Szatmár-Beregi steppe near the Ukrainian border. The habitat is described as grassy slopes and forest steppe. The primary food plants of the larvae are *Vicia cracca* and *Vicia tenuifolia*. The larvae live with ants and hibernate in the L2 stage. Adults fly in one generation from late May to early July.

2023

In the Bakony Mountains (Tési Plateau), it flew in large numbers in early June 2022 and was the dominant species (Hudák 2023). At several points on the plateau, the altitude exceeds 500 meters above sea level. Characteristic vegetation types: beech forests, oak forests, cleared meadows, hay meadows, gradually scrubby mountain meadows. No one has reported such a mass occurrence in the 21st century. The author has observed it in several locations in the Vértes and South Gerecse mountains.

2025

Distribution in Hungary only found in a few locations so far, with most specimens originating from the Budapest area, and a few records from the Vértes, Bakony, Balaton Uplands, and Szatmár-Beregi Plain. Rare everywhere. Flight period: from the end of May to the beginning of July. The larvae are dark green, with a reddish-brown back edged with white and jagged side lines. Host plant(s): *Lathyrus pratensis*, *Vicia cracca*, *Onobrychis viciifolia* (See: <https://jasius.hu/lepidopterology>).

Biotopes and bionomics: Some populations live in dry, warm locations (biotopes such as dry meadows and forest steppes), mostly on limestone substrates. Others live in damp and cold locations and peat bog biotopes. Imago: VI-VII(VIII) in one generation. The green caterpillar lives VII-V (hibernating) on *Vicia cracca*, and according to literature also on *Lathyrus pratensis* and *Medicago sativa*. It is myrmecophilous and pupates on the ground. Geographical distribution: North Africa, Europe (except Great Britain, northern Scandinavia, central and northern France, Belgium and Holland), Turkey, Russia to the Far East. Widespread in Bohemia (still spreading), only occasionally in Moravia and Poland. Rare in Slovakia (Borská nížina lowlands), occasionally in Hungary, only in locations with limestone substrate. Occasionally in Austria (Mühlviertel, Wachau). Also known from the Carpathian Ukraine. Note: Not threatened in the Czech Republic, expanding, while in Slovakia only known from the south-west of the country.

Outlook for Central Europe**1975**

The research results of Marschner (1975) are extremely interesting. *Plebicula amanda* is characterised by a strong capacity for dispersal and geographical range expansion. Since the early twentieth century, the species has expanded westwards from eastern Central Europe, progressively colonising northern Germany, Saxony, and neighboring regions. Early records from newly occupied areas frequently involved worn individuals, indicating immigration. Within a short period, however, repeated observations of fresh adults and larval findings demonstrated the establishment of stable, resident populations, suggesting successful local reproduction following dispersal.

Adult behaviour shows marked sexual and age-related differences. Freshly emerged adults display calm flight behaviour and regularly visit flowers, particularly those associated with larval host plants. Flight activity is strongly dependent on favourable weather conditions. Older males become increasingly restless, exhibiting rapid and erratic flight and rarely settling. Females are generally inconspicuous, remaining concealed within dense vegetation and showing limited flight activity during most of the day. Increased female activity is mainly observed in the late afternoon, when individuals fly close to the ground over host plant patches. Although sustained long-distance flight in females is rarely observed directly, their role in large-scale dispersal is inferred from the documented pattern of range expansion.

Larvae develop on *Vicia cracca*, confirming local reproduction in newly colonised areas. The species occupies a wide range of habitats, with a preference for ruderal sites, but also occurs in semi-natural wet habitats, indicating high ecological plasticity.

1976

According to Forster & Wohlfahrt (1976) the species has an eastern distribution and is absent from central and western Germany, Belgium, and the Netherlands. Within south-eastern Central Europe, its occurrence is highly localized. In recent decades, however, the species has exhibited a westward expansion of its range. Adults are univoltine, with flight activity recorded from June to August. The eggs are whitish and sea-urchin-like, characterized by polygonal cells with protruding corners that create a reticulated surface structure. The larva is dark green, bearing a reddish-brown dorsal stripe edged in white and two lateral stripes interrupted with red. The subdorsal stripes are white, and the head is black. The species feeds on *Vicia* spp. and overwinters in the larval stage.

1989

Reiprich & Okáli (1989) mention only one site in Slovakia: Brezová pod Bradlom. Slamka (2004) named another site: Borská nížina (near Bratislava).

2004

Biotopes and bionomics: Some populations live in dry, warm locations (biotopes such as dry meadows and forest steppes), mostly on limestone substrates. Others live in damp and cold locations and peat bog biotopes. Imago: VI–VII. (VIII) in one generation. The green caterpillar lives VII–V (hibernating) on *Vicia cracca*, and according to literature also on *Lathyrus pratensis* and *Medicago sativa*. It is myrmecophilous and pupates on the ground. Geographical distribution: North Africa, Europe (except Great Britain, northern Scandinavia, central and northern France, Belgium and Holland), Turkey, Russia to the Far East. Widespread in Bohemia (still spreading), only occasionally in Moravia and Poland. Rare in Slovakia (Borská nížina lowlands), occasionally in Hungary, only in locations with limestone substrate. Occasionally in Austria (Mühlviertel, Wachau). Also known from the Carpathian Ukraine. Note: Not threatened in the Czech Republic, expanding, while in Slovakia only known from the south-west of the country (Slamka 2004).

View towards the east and towards the Balkans**1988 – “Yugoslavia”**

Jakšić (1988) presented the geographical distribution of Rhopalocera species in the former Yugoslavia on a detailed UTM map. He marked numerous sites on the maps, including the *P. amandus* species, mainly from mountainous regions. Looking at the map, the populations are highly fragmented. We cannot find any Croatian or Serbian sites close to the mountainous regions of Transdanubia in Hungary.

2008 – Romania

It is important that we can compare areas neighboring Hungary, so Romania was particularly interesting. The *P. amandus* was rediscovered in Romania during surveys conducted in May 2007 in the Babadag forest, Tulcea County. A fresh specimen collected there represents the first confirmed record of the species in Dobrogea after 78 years and in Romania after nearly three decades. Historical data indicate that the species was previously reported from Ciucurova, approximately 20 km west of Babadag, suggesting continuity of suitable habitats in the region. Although the overall distribution of *P. amandus* covers Romania relatively evenly, records are sparse and often outdated, leaving significant gaps in knowledge. In contrast, the species is widespread in neighboring countries such as Ukraine, Moldova, and Bulgaria. Several Romanian populations appear to have gone extinct, including the formerly abundant population at Fânațele Clujului, which has disappeared despite the area's protected status and rich butterfly diversity. The species is listed as endangered in the Red List of Romanian Rhopalocera, with regional populations ranging from data-deficient to endangered. Its rarity and decline remain unexplained, highlighting the need for targeted ecological and distributional studies. As *P. amandus* is legally protected in Romania and occurs within a protected area, further research and conservation measures are strongly justified. This rediscovery underscores both the fragility of butterfly populations in Romania and the importance of continued monitoring in under-studied regions (see Dincă & Vila 2008). Székely (2008, p. 136) shows only seven sites on the map in his book, but these are geographically very distant from the Hungarian population fragments.

In his book on the Ostrogovich collection, Popescu-Gorj (1964) reported several specimens from the Cluj site from the period between 1928 and 1932. He also mentions a male specimen of “f. *stigmatica* Schultz”. König (1975) reported only one male specimen from Cheile Nerei in 1974.

2005 – Ukraine

According to Nekrutenko & Tsikolovets (2005), it is found everywhere in Ukraine except for the dry steppes and the Carpathian Mountains. It occurs in meadows, wet forest clearings, and groves.

Discussion

The present study provides the first comprehensive, chronologically structured synthesis of data on *Polyommatus amandus* in Hungary, integrating more than 150 years of faunistic, ecological, and biogeographical information. The results reveal pronounced long-term fluctuations, severe regional declines, and a strongly fragmented contemporary distribution, contrasting with the species' international IUCN status of Least Concern. Taken together, the historical record and recent observations highlight the species' vulnerability within Hungary and underscore the need for targeted conservation and monitoring.

A central finding is that *P. amandus* has experienced substantial contraction across its former range in Hungary. While 19th- and early 20th-century reports documented the species in several mountain ranges (e.g., Mecsek, Bakony, Buda Hills, Gödöllő Hills), many of these populations have not been confirmed for decades. Multiple sources indicate local extinctions, particularly in the Mecsek Mountains, where the species has not been reliably recorded for more than a century. Similar local declines were noted in the Bakony region, where historical pine–oak forest habitats have largely disappeared due to forestry and mining activities. These patterns suggest that habitat alteration—especially the loss of semi-natural meadows, forest-steppe mosaics, and traditional orchard systems—has played a major role in population decline.

Despite these losses, the study also identifies several areas where *P. amandus* persists or has recently been rediscovered. The confirmation of the species near Sopron–Görbehalom in the eastern Alpine foothills (based on material from 1978) was particularly significant, demonstrating western persistence in habitats characterized by humid meadows and transitional wet grasslands. More recently, high local abundance observed on the Tési Plateau (Bakony Mountains) in 2022 represents an exceptional record: no mass occurrence of similar magnitude had been reported in Hungary in the 21st century. This finding suggests that suitable habitat patches, when maintained through low-intensity management or natural processes, can still support large populations. The emergence of new records from the Szatmár–Beregi Plain further indicates that the species may be under-detected in certain regions, particularly mesophilic-hygrophilous transitional zones.

A persistent theme throughout historical literature is the inconsistency or ambiguity surrounding the species' ecological requirements and larval host plants. Early authors noted only *Vicia cracca*, while later studies added *V. hirsuta* (Bink 1992), *V. tenuifolia* (Lafranchis 2019), *V. tetrasperma* (Bink 1992), *V. villosa* (Lafranchis 2019), *Lathyrus pratensis* (Lafranchis 2019), *L. sylvestris* (Lafranchis et al. 2015), *Medicago sativa* (Eliasson 2005), *Securigera varia* (Tugulea 2016). This expanding list may reflect genuine ecological flexibility but may also stem from identifications or differences in methodology. Furthermore, several authors commented on unexplained rarity despite widespread host plants, suggesting that factors other than trophic specialization—such as microclimate, soil type (especially limestone substrates), and ant associations—contribute to population viability. The species' myrmecophilous larval stage, combined with overwintering in L2, likely increases sensitivity to microhabitat disturbance and moisture balance.

The Hungarian trends align with broader Central and Eastern European patterns. While *P. amandus* is expanding in parts of the Czech Republic and remains widespread in Ukraine and Moldova, it is rare and highly localized in Slovakia, Austria, and Romania. The rediscovery of the species in Romania after several decades further highlights both the species' patchy detectability and the fragility of its Central European populations. Differences among neighboring countries underscore the importance of regional habitat structure: *P. amandus* appears to respond strongly to the presence of limestone bedrock, semi-natural grassland mosaics, and stable mesophilic-hygrophilous microclimates.

Overall, the historical evidence demonstrates that *P. amandus* in Hungary is in a long-term

Fig. 7. Habitus image of the wing pattern of the male and female *Polyommatus amandus*: **7a)** Hungary, Pomáz, 28.v.2014; **7b)** Serbia, Stara Planina, 18.vi.2022 (photo: © P.Gergely)

state of decline, punctuated by isolated local recoveries. The inconsistency between its global conservation status (Least Concern) and its national situation underscores the need for region-specific assessments. Preserving remaining populations will require the protection and restoration of both dry limestone grasslands and humid meadow systems, maintenance of traditional low-intensity land use, and long-term monitoring in order to document fluctuations and identify previously overlooked populations.

In conclusion, this study clarifies the historical trajectory and status of *P. amandus* in Hungary, demonstrating marked population fragmentation, significant regional losses, and occasional local resurgence. These findings highlight the species as a conservation priority at the national scale and provide an essential foundation for future ecological, genetic, and conservation-based research.

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Table 1. Chronological Overview of Key Publications on *Polyommatus amandus* in Hungary

Year	Source / Author	Summary of Key Contribution
1846	Nendtvich	First mention from Pécs (Mecsek Mts.), mentioned as “ <i>icarius</i> ”.
1896	Abafi-Aigner et al.	Reports six sites in historic Hungary; after Trianon, only Budapest and Pécs remain.
1907	Abafi-Aigner	Notes sporadic occurrence, two generations (May–Aug); larvae on <i>Vicia cracca</i> .
1953	Kovács	Lists seven Hungarian localities (Gödöllő Hills, Mecsek, Vértes, Buda Hills).
1956	Szabó	Identifies the species as one of the rarest; key localities: Szár and Pomáz; rarity attributed (unclearly) to “climatological factors.”
1968	Gozmány	Describes it as very rare; known from few sites in Transdanubia and Gödöllő Hills; host plant <i>Vicia cracca</i> .
1979	Rézbányai	Reports a Bakony (Fenyőfő) population; considers it a Siberian faunal element; habitat likely altered or lost; population presumed extinct.
1987	Fazekas	Documents a new site at Sopron–Görbehalom; confirms persistence in W Hungary; discusses taxonomic placement (<i>Plebicula</i>).
1989	Varga	Classified species as potentially endangered; small, isolated populations with fluctuating abundance.
1994	Bálint	States presence in all limestone regions; populations scattered and small; notes lack biological data.
1996	Bálint	Describes habitat types (hay meadows, orchards, pastures); adult behavior and food plants; species protected.
1997	Dietzel	Emphasizes rarity; notes mesophilic habitats in Bakony; highlights threats from land-use changes and chemical drift.
2006	Bálint et al.	Museum catalogue: provides specimen data and habitat descriptions; lists additional larval host plants.
2006	Fazekas	Historical Pécs specimen (1891) discussed; species extinct in the Mecsek despite suitable habitats.
2017	Gergely et al.	Comprehensive modern account; species rare, mainly in Transdanubia; new data from Szatmár-Beregi Plain; confirms larval hosts and life cycle.
2023	Hudák	Reports unusually abundant population on the Tési Plateau (Bakony Mts.) largest 21st-century occurrence.
2025	Recent Hungarian data	Species rare and localized; flight period late May–early July; larvae on several <i>Vicia</i> and <i>Lathyrus</i> species; occurs on limestone and in both dry and wet habitats.

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